

Identification of Chemical Constituents in *Blumea balsamifera* using UPLC-Q-Orbitrap HRMS and Evaluation of Their Antioxidant Activities

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Figure S1. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of α,α -Trehalose

Figure S2. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of D-(-)-Fructose

Figure S3. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of gentisic acid 5-O- β -glucoside

Figure S4. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Caffeic acid

Figure S5. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Tuberonic acid glucoside

Figure S6. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Hemiphloin

Figure S7. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Taxifolin

Figure S8. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Rutin

Figure S9. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Quercetin-3 β -D-glucoside

Figure S10. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Quercetin

Figure S11. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Quercetin-3-Arabinoside

Figure S12. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Cynaroside

Figure S13. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of 1,3-Dicaffeoylquinic acid

Figure S14. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Chlorogenic acid

Figure S15. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside

Figure S16. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of 4-oxo-5-phenylpentanoic acid

Figure S17. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Eriodictyol

Figure S18. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Padmatin

Figure S19. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Isorhamnetin

Figure S20. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Naringenin

Figure S21. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of 7-O-Methylaromadendrin

Figure S22. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Aurantio-obtusin

Figure S23. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Fraxetin

Figure S24. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Hematoxylin

Figure S25. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Sakuranetin

Figure S26. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Aurantiamide acetate

Figure S27. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Cryptotanshinone

Figure S28. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Nootkatone

Figure S29. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of N-Phenyl-1-naphthylamine

Figure S30. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Tanshinone IIA

Figure S31. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Citroflex A-4

Figure S32. TICs of *Blumea balsamifera* (L.) DC. in negative ion mode

Figure S33. TICs of *Blumea balsamifera* (L.) DC. in positive ion mode

ANX-100%JC-Nd #952 RT: 0.86 AV: 1 NL: 2.55E5
F: FTMS - p ESI d Full ms2 341.1084@hcd40.00 [50.0000-368.6956]

Figure S1. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of α,α -Trehalose

ANX-100%JC-Nd #941 RT: 0.85 AV: 1 NL: 5.14E5
F: FTMS - p ESI d Full ms2 179.0558@hcd40.00 [40.6804-203.4019]

Figure S2. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of D-(-)-Fructose

ANX-100%JC-Nd #2422 RT: 2.15 AV: 1 NL: 1.59E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 315.0504@hcd40.00 [50.0000-342.1164]

Figure S3. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of gentisic acid 5-O- β -glucoside

ANX-100%JC-Nd #6705 RT: 5.93 AV: 1 NL: 1.05E6
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 179.0558@hcd40.00 [40.6804-203.4019]

Figure S4. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Caffeic acid

ANX-100%JC-Nd #8187 RT: 7.23 AV: 1 NL: 2.21E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 387.1140@hcd40.00 [50.0000-415.6212]

Figure S5. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Tuberonic acid glucoside

ANX-100%JC-Nd #11533 RT: 10.18 AV: 1 NL: 3.45E6
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 433.1142@hcd40.00 [50.0000-462.5415]

Figure S6. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Hemiphloin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #11762 RT: 10.38 AV: 1 NL: 1.66E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 303.1348@hcd40.00 [50.0000-329.9625]

Figure S7. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Taxifolin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #11827 RT: 10.44 AV: 1 NL: 1.12E6
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 609.1390@hcd40.00 [64.2087-642.0867]

Figure S8. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Rutin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #12480 RT: 11.02 AV: 1 NL: 1.73E6
F: FTMS - p ESI d Full ms2 463.0877@hcd40.00 [50.0000-493.1144]

Figure S9. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Quercetin-3 β -D-glucoside

ANX-100%JC-Pd #12781 RT: 11.14 AV: 1 NL: 6.41E5
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 303.0498@hcd40.00 [50.0000-329.8758]

Figure S10. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Quercetin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #13649 RT: 12.05 AV: 1 NL: 2.77E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 433.0110@hcd40.00 [50.0000-462.4362]

Figure S11. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Quercetin-3-Arabinoside

ANX-100%JC-Nd #13684 RT: 12.08 AV: 1 NL: 4.08E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 447.0297@hcd40.00 [50.0000-476.7353]

Figure S12. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Cynaroside

ANX-100%JC-Nd #14166 RT: 12.50 AV: 1 NL: 1.39E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 515.1196@hcd40.00 [54.6187-546.1871]

Figure S13. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of 1,3-Dicaffeoylquinic acid

ANX-100%JC-Nd #14371 RT: 12.68 AV: 1 NL: 6.78E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 353.0871@hcd40.00 [50.0000-380.9139]

Figure S14. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Chlorogenic acid

ANX-100%JC-Nd #14806 RT: 13.07 AV: 1 NL: 1.01E5
F: FTMS - p ESI d Full ms2 477.1795@hcd40.00 [50.7488-507.4881]

Figure S15. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Isorhamnetin-3-O-glucoside

ANX-100%JC-Pd #15453 RT: 13.47 AV: 1 NL: 1.29E6
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 193.0498@hcd40.00 [43.5352-217.6758]

Figure S16. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of 4-oxo-5-phenylpentanoic acid

ANX-100%JC-Nd #18449 RT: 16.28 AV: 1 NL: 4.94E6
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 287.0438@hcd40.00 [50.0000-313.5497]

Figure S17. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Eriodictyol

ANX-100%JC-Nd #20150 RT: 17.78 AV: 1 NL: 1.20E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 317.0050@hcd40.00 [50.0000-344.1101]

Figure S18. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Padmatin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #20340 RT: 17.95 AV: 1 NL: 8.66E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 315.0504@hcd40.00 [50.0000-342.1164]

Figure S19. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Isorhamnetin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #20830 RT: 18.39 AV: 1 NL: 4.52E5
F: FTMS -p ESI d Full ms2 271.0612@hcd40.00 [50.0000-297.2475]

Figure S20. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Naringenin

ANX-100%JC-Pd #21939 RT: 19.12 AV: 1 NL: 1.19E5
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 303.0498@hcd40.00 [50.0000-329.8758]

Figure S21. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of 7-O-Methylaromadendrin

ANX-100%JC-Pd #22293 RT: 19.43 AV: 1 NL: 2.59E6
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 331.0812@hcd40.00 [50.0000-358.4678]

Figure S22. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Aurantio-obtusin

ANX-100%JC-Pd #22218 RT: 19.36 AV: 1 NL: 6.01E5
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 209.0809@hcd40.00 [46.8055-234.0275]

Figure S23. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Fraxetin

ANX-100%JC-Nd #22430 RT: 19.80 AV: 1 NL: 2.52E7
F: FTMS - p ESI d Full ms2 301.0712@hcd40.00 [50.0000-327.8576]

Figure S24. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Hematoxylin

ANX-100%JC-Pd #23704 RT: 20.66 AV: 1 NL: 1.72E6
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 287.0552@hcd40.00 [50.0000-313.5613]

Figure S25. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Sakuranetin

ANX-100%JC-Pd #24688 RT: 21.51 AV: 1 NL: 8.11E6
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 445.2120@hcd40.00 [50.0000-474.8813]

Figure S26. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Aurantiamide acetate

ANX-100%JC-Pd #26440 RT: 23.04 AV: 1 NL: 1.83E5
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 297.1484@hcd40.00 [50.0000-323.8564]

Figure S27. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Cryptotanshinone

ANX-100%JC-Pd #26678 RT: 23.24 AV: 1 NL: 1.05E6
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 219.1743@hcd40.00 [48.8646-244.3228]

Figure S28. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Nootkatone

ANX-100%JC-Pd #26723 RT: 23.28 AV: 1 NL: 1.85E6
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 220.1694@hcd40.00 [49.0676-245.3378]

Figure S29. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of N-Phenyl-1-naphthylamine

ANX-100%JC-Pd #27625 RT: 24.07 AV: 1 NL: 2.00E5
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 295.1904@hcd40.00 [50.0000-321.8592]

Figure S30. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Tanshinone IIA

ANX-100%JC-Pd #28354 RT: 24.70 AV: 1 NL: 6.52E5
F: FTMS + p ESI d Full ms2 403.2398@hcd40.00 [50.0000-432.0696]

Figure S31. MS² fragmentation spectra (CID) of Citroflex A-4

RT: 0.00 - 29.01 SM: 5G

NL: 1.24E9
Base Peak F:
FTMS - p ESI Full
ms
[100.0000-
1500.0000] MS
ANX-100%JC-Nd

Figure S32. TICs of *Blumea balsamifera* (L.) DC. in negative ion mode

RT: 0.00 - 29.01 SM: 5G

Figure S33. TICs of *Blumea balsamifera* (L.) DC. in positive ion mode